

VOCATIONAL GUIDANCE OF SCHOOLCHILDREN WITH THE HELP OF MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. This article summarizes the existing problems in the correct orientation of students to the profession, shortcomings in practice, ways to eliminate them.

Keywords: choosing the right profession, socialization, self-assessment, technological education, continuous system, cooperation, interdisciplinary communication.

ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ ОРИЕНТАЦИЯ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ С ПОМОЩЬЮ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

Аннотация. В данной статье обобщены существующие проблемы в правильной ориентации студентов на профессию, недостатки на практике, пути их устранения.

Ключевые слова: выбор профессии, социализация, самооценка, технологическое образование, непрерывная система, сотрудничество, междисциплинарная связь.

It is known that the prosperity, social, political, economic stability of any society depends on the high level of development of the mental and moral potential of its citizens.

According to paragraph 12 of the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan “on measures to further improve the system of training personnel in working professions” dated June 8, 2021 PQ-5140, the procedure for vocational training of students of grades 9-11 of general secondary educational institutions was adopted for reference.

After all, in the spiritual renewal of our society, in the formation of a socially oriented market economy, the national issue of Personnel Training, the construction of a democratic collective state, which ensures its integration into the world community, plays an important role as a priority criterion. As a human child matures, he plunges into science and enlightenment. He also takes the initial lesson from school. But teaching young people who are the owners of our future it is natural that some of the problems associated with teaching them are making a person think today. This is because the modern society continues to have a reputation for mature knowledgeable staff.

Today, many innovations are being created and put into practice aimed at modernizing the content of education, improving the quality of education, the widespread introduction of innovative technologies in education. The effectiveness of these innovations largely depends on the correct Organization of innovative activities carried out in the educational institution. In order to modernize the educational process, prepare specialists in accordance with the requirements of the world, to be able to follow the learner in the educational process, both pedagogical and innovative skills should be at a high level in the teacher.

One of the most relevant tasks in the field of pedagogy is the upbringing of a strong, educated, independent-minded person in every possible way. It is important in this that independent work is organized in the lesson and practical training. In the current conditions, where

the flow of information and the range of knowledge is rapidly expanding, it is difficult to convey all information only to the lesson-students, of course. Therefore, teachers should pay special attention to the correct Organization of independent work of students. Information technology is increasingly entering human life every day. Today, even the most ancient professions require computer programs and various IT technologies. In this regard, an informatics course was introduced in schools, since children learn much easier and faster than adults. In addition, almost all modern schoolchildren have a computer at home, they are happy to improve their knowledge after school.

Studying at the university requires the student to have minimal knowledge in the field of computer technology. Increasingly, teachers are demanding that tests, coursework and abstracts in Computer Science and supplements to them be presented to the review only in printed form. Therefore, the prospective student cannot do without learning text editors and some other useful programs. It should also be noted that computer skills acquired during computer science classes will be useful both in the study of the humanities and in the study of the Exact Sciences. Computer science is a leader in such communication of various topics and disciplines. Some experts believe that computer knowledge from a school Informatics course may not be useful to all schoolchildren in the future, and therefore they question the feasibility of teaching this subject in high schools. But if we take into account the professional orientation of graduates, then this topic of the school curriculum will become very necessary and necessary for study. It is much easier for young people who have tried themselves in the field of computer technology to choose their future profession. Informatics is understood as a natural result of the historical development of the information sphere of society.

School computer science cannot include all the diverse information that makes up the content of the actively developing science of Informatics. At the same time, the subject of the school, which performs general educational functions, should reflect the most important, basic concepts and information that reveal the essence of science, arm students with the knowledge, skills and skills necessary to learn the basics of other disciplines. at school, as well as preparing young people for future practical activities and life in a modern Information Society. To focus on the profession, the Informatics course must provide students with information about the professions directly related to computing and informatics, as well as the various applications of the subjects studied at school using computers. In addition to the production side of the issue, the practical goals of teaching Informatics also imply the "daily" aspect - the preparation of young people for the rational use of computer technology and other information and communication technologies in everyday life.

The educational goal of the school Informatics course is primarily ensured by the strong influence of the worldview of students, which has awareness of the capabilities and role of computing technologies and information technology tools in the development of society and civilization. all. The contribution of the school Informatics course to the scientific worldview of schoolchildren is determined by the formation of the idea of information, which is one of the three main concepts of Science: Matter, energy and information, which is the basis of the modern scientific structure, pictures of the world. In addition, when studying computer science at a qualitatively new stage, a culture of mental labor is formed and such important universal features

as planning one's work, its rational execution, critical connection with the real process of its implementation are formed.

The initial and at the same time extremely important stage of the process of professional formation involves the choice of the future profession, that is, the period until the arrival of a specific professional decision. It is clear that the level of preparation of young people for the choice of a profession is not just an attachment to age characteristics, it does not form on its own by a certain age. The choice of profession of young people should be prepared and brought up through pedagogical-psychological knowledge, skills, qualifications, as well as the influence of society. In this process, a person is required to have knowledge of the profession. Therefore, it is necessary to arm students with knowledge about the world of professions and to develop practical skills and qualifications. To do this, it is necessary to provide manuals on professions, handouts. Only then will we have the opportunity to consciously send students-young people to the profession, avoiding various difficulties, conflicts, obstacles that arise in the process of choosing a profession.

A technology teacher school practicing psychologist must carry out the following in the process of his professional activity:

- to introduce students to the types of professions necessary for the life and development of society;
- to organize tips of a pedagogical-psychological nature for guiding students to the profession;
- formation of stable interests in students in certain professions, taking into account their personal qualities;
- to acquaint students with famous personalities who gained fame as a result of their professional activities and their contributions to the development of society and humanity;
- informing students about the role of professions in the development of economic, social, spiritual aspects of society;
- conduct conversations with parents of students on the orientation of their children to a worthy profession;
- informing students of the negative consequences of choosing the wrong profession;
- create favorable conditions for students to form and test initial universal and professional skills;
- in order to guide students to the right profession, to study their personality, type of Labor and interests in professions;
- Organization of exhibitions, conferences, meetings at the school, telling about specific professions, their socio-economic significance, in order to ensure the effectiveness of the process of sending students to the profession;
- conduct a regular pedagogical-psychological diagnosis in order to determine the personal-professional interests of students.

When choosing a profession, the propaganda and propaganda work of the school practitioner-psychologist is also important.

When to start a career rejuvenation? the answer to the question "What is the difference?" was received in the following diagram. 57% of students believe that vocational guidance should be started from school. 22% of students believe this should start at kindergarten, and 14% believe that the selection phase should start from college.

In place of the conclusion, it is worth noting that directing our young people to the right profession, I would like to emphasize once again that this is one of the most important vases. It is a law that does not require proof that a person, by choosing the right profession, gives a huge welcome to his family, to society.

Today, much attention is paid to digital technologies in Jahan, including Uzbekistan. This situation can also be seen on the example of the intellectual knowledge base, which is increasingly used in our society, Khoshimova Maftunabonu's article in this regard is devoted to the orientation of schoolchildren to the profession with the help of modern information technology.

The problems raised in the article were halved by the author using reliable sources. This information includes facts, data, research, reports, articles and other relevant information related to specific directions or interests. with the help of modern information technology, the purpose of vocational guidance for schoolchildren is to provide a centralized and easily accessible repository of information that can be used to make informed decisions, solve problems and answer questions.

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